

THE REACTIVITY OF SULFHYDRYL GROUPS IN PROTEINS. PART I. AMANDIN

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Silver, *p*-chloromercuribenzoate and ferricyanide were allowed to react on amandin, both native and denatured. Native amandin possesses one "sluggish SH group" per molecule. No "masked SH group" becomes available after denaturation in 7.5 *M*-urea. Ferricyanide is not specific for the SH groups in all proteins.

Native amandin is reported to possess no SH group. Yet the only reagents used to detect them have been oxidising agents: nitroprusside and phosphotungstic acid (Burk *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 120, 63), porphyrindin (Greenstein, *ibid.*, 1939, 128, 233) and iodide-iodate (Hess *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1943, 151, 635).

To warrant this assertion, amandin should be treated with reagents able to react with isolated thiols and "sluggish SH groups" (Helferman *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1943, 157, 445).

Silver and *p*-chloromercuribenzoate were therefore used as the most powerful selective SH reagents known.

Diluted ferricyanide, under well determined conditions, oxidises only the SH groups in ovalbumin (Anson, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1939, 22, 247). The reaction is stoichiometrical and does not go beyond the disulphide stage. It therefore requires the close proximity of two SH groups. But, the action of ferricyanide on other reducing groups of proteins has never been systematically studied. So, it remained questionable if its specificity for the SH groups extended to proteins other than ovalbumin. It was tentatively applied to amandin.

Argentometric Amperometric Titrations.— $\text{Ag}(\text{NH}_3)_2^+$, a mercaptide-forming reagent, attacks always a maximum number of SH groups. The method of Kolthoff and Harris (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1946, 18, 167) was adapted to semi-micro dosages by using a vibrating electrode according to Rosenberg *et al.* (*Anal. Chem.*, 1950, 22, 1185). The HgI_2 reference cell was replaced by an Ag/AgCl one and a potential of -0.2V was applied to the vibrating Pt electrode. The microammeter was a W. G. Pye Cambridge, with a maximum deflection of 95 mm. per μA . It was shunted by extra resistances regulated to obtain the desired sensibility.

The titrating solutions (0.005 or 0.001 *M*- AgNO_3) were added dropwise with a microburette. An equal volume of buffer solution (0.6 *M*- NH_4NO_3 and 0.1 *M*- NH_3) at *pH* 9.25 was added to the 2-3% protein solutions just before starting the titrations. For each protein a whole set of determinations were performed on volumes of solution ranging from 1 ml. to 20 ml. Subjective influences of one determination on the other, in the ammeter readings and in the drawing of the two lines extrapolation of, which furnished the end-point, were thus avoided.

p-Chloromercuribenzoate.—*p*-Chloromercuribenzoate (*p*-ClHg-b), another mercaptide-forming reagent, should be more sensitive to steric hindrances. The back-titration of an excess of *p*-ClHg-b by cysteine, in presence of nitroprusside, according to Mac Donnell *et al.* (*Arch. Biochim. Biophys.*, 1951, 32, 288) was adapted to microquantities, thanks to an "Agl" microsyringe. *p*-ClHg-b was synthesised from *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride *via* *p*-toluenesulphonate and *p* tolylmercuric chloride according to Whitmore (Gilman & Blatt, "Organic Syntheses", 1947, pp. 492, 519, 159). *p*-Chloromercuribenzoic acid (200 g.) was dissolved in 100 ml. of 0.01 *M*-NaOH. The solution was filtered before each set of determinations. The nitroprusside was prepared by crushing together one part of nitroprusside (B. D. H.) and two of Na₂CO₃ 'pro analysi'. On a porcelain spotting-plate, several 0.1 ml. *p*-ClHg-b drops were placed. To one half of the drops 0.2 ml. of distilled water was added and to the other half, 0.2 ml. of the 2-3% protein solution. After 1 hour of contact, a few mg. of the nitroprusside were added. The excess *p*-ClHg-b was titrated by a fresh 0.005 *M* cysteine solution until a rosy colour persisted for a few moments under gentle stirring. The difference between the blank and protein titrations expresses the amount of SH groups undergoing reaction. Results were reproducible up to 0.005 μ *M* of cysteine.

Ferricyanide.—Anson's method (*loc.cit.*) was slightly modified. The ferrocyanide formed was directly determined. At 4000–4200 Å, ferrocyanide absorbs only 4% of what ferricyanide does. A standard curve for ferro-ferricyanide mixtures in different proportions was established under the conditions of the actual SH determinations, with a spectrophotometer (Beckman Du) at 4100 Å and 4200 Å and 25°. A linear relation between ferricyanide concentration and extinction was observed for concentrations from 2×10^{-5} *M* to 2×10^{-4} *M*. Determinations were made as follows: 4 ml. of a 2-3% protein solution and 4 ml. distilled water were introduced into separate 100 ml. volumetric flasks. *M*/6-Neutral phosphate buffer (1 ml.) and a 0.004 *M* ferrocyanide solution (5 ml.) were added to both. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 15 minutes at 25°. Water was then added up to the mark, and 10 ml. was pipetted into a test-tube and 1 ml. of a 30% trichloroacetic acid solution added. The precipitated protein was filtered off and the extinction of the filtrate measured at 25°. By reading on the standard curve, the quantity of ferrocyanide corresponding to the difference between the extinctions of protein solution and blank, one can eventually know the number of SH groups involved in the reaction. Readings were repeated at 4100 Å and 4200 Å and precipitations made several times for each determination.

Proteins.—All concentration determinations were carried out by semimicro Kjeldhal. Protein solutions were prepared from freeze-dried preparations and stored in the cold room under toluene for never more than 20 days. Denaturation was carried out as follows: To 10 ml. of a 3% protein solution in a 20 ml. volumetric flask 9 g. of urea was added. Distilled water was then added slowly to dissolve the urea and bring the solution to the mark (7.5 *M* in urea). The solutions were left for 1 hour at 25° before titration, unless the time of contact was otherwise specified.

To compare the literature data with ours, the percentages of cysteine reported were eventually converted into SH/*M* on the basis of the *M. W.* adopted by us.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation.—We are indebted to Prof. P. Putzeys for the amandin, prepared by an unpublished method. The ground almonds were defatted by a 10% NaCl—0.1% NaHCO₃ solution. After Büchner filtration, the extract was clarified on kieselguhr and CaCl₂. The solution was saturated with MgSO₄ and the precipitate discarded. By adding an equal volume of a saturated (NH₄)₂SO₄ solution the amandin was precipitated. It was dissolved in the solvent and reprecipitated several times. It was finally dialysed against 0.3M-NH₄NO₃. As few or no SH groups were expected, 5-7% amandin solutions were used. Dilution with the ammonium buffer solution before the silver amperometric titrations was replaced by the addition of a few drops of NH₃ (3M) to the 0.3 M-NH₄NO₃ solution so as to bring it to *p*_H 9.25.

The M.W. was assumed to be 385,000 (Moody, Thesis, Wisconsin Univ., 1944) and the N%, 18.65.

TABLE I

	Ag (NH ₃) ₂ ⁺			p-ChloroHg benzoate.			Fe(CN) ₆ ⁴⁻	
	% Cyst.	SH/M.	No. of determ.	% Cyst.	SH/M.	No. of determ.	Reduced Fe ³⁺ /M.	No. of determ.
Native protein.								
	0.036	1.2	9	0.04	1.3	6	5	4
Protein denatured in urea (7.5M)								
Time of contact.								
½ hr.	0.027	0.9	2					
24	0.015	0.5	2	0.036	1.2	6	5	2
96	0.006	0.2	2					

Five molecules of ferricyanide are reduced per molecule of amandin, while silver and p-ClHg-b react with about 1 SH/M. It is most unlikely that ferricyanide would affect five times more SH groups than the strongest reagents. Moreover, other equally effective oxidising agents failed to detect any free SH group in amandin. Most probably ferricyanide oxidises other groups (tyrosine, tryptophane etc.) and thus cannot be considered as a universally specific reagent for proteinic thiols.

Silver and p-ClHg-b titrations show the presence of a little more than one "sluggish SH group" per molecule of amandin. This group is probably responsible for the qualitative positive reaction with nitroprusside and phosphotungstic acid after denaturation by urea, mentioned by Burk (*loc.cit.*). He also noticed that amandin in 6.6M urea solution had split into sub-units of M.W. 30,000. The detection of a single "sluggish SH group"/M, would imply that these sub-units are not all perfectly identical.

Amandin seems to be a heterogeneous protein (Barré, *Bull. soc. chim. Biol.*, 1953, 35, 899, 917). SH determinations should therefore be made on each fraction to detect the possible existence of a "mercaptamandin". Hess *et al.* (*loc.cit.*) found no cysteine

but 28 cystine/M in amandin, hydrolysed by 20% HCl and 6N-H₂SO₄. An inference from such analysis to the cysteine present in the native molecule, however, remains doubtful.

The slow decrease in the number of SH groups detected by Ag, observed with longer times of contact between amandin and urea, is probably due to a spontaneous oxidation by air and the formation of an intermolecular disulphide bond between two sub-units of amandin.

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